

WAYS TO IMPROVE THE STRUCTURE OF SMALL BUSINESS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *Ensuring the smoothness of the formation of the structural structure of small entrepreneurship in the economic sectors of Uzbekistan, measures to increase the efficiency of the structural structure of small entrepreneurship, the approach in terms of special blocks in determining the measures to increase the efficiency of the structural structure of small entrepreneurship, the effectiveness of the structural structure of small entrepreneurship in blocks and measures within a specific block assessment of the processes of formation of the structural structure of small businesses in Uzbekistan market and administrative levers of regulation are studied.*

Keywords: *small business, specialization, network, structural structure of small business, stability, special blocks, market and administrative levers.*

1.Introduction

In the world, in the conditions of globalization and international competition, research is being conducted on the scientific-methodological basis of improving the structural structure of small businesses. The effect of improving the structural structure of small businesses on job creation and employment, introducing innovations, researching their place in technological development, developing strategies to support small businesses to increase the volume of exports, improving

their access to financial resources, studying the possibilities of lending and attracting investments, by the state implementation of incentive policies, legal frameworks and ensuring their effectiveness, the contribution of small business to national economic growth, social stability and economic Researching the impact on diversification, studying the characteristics of the development of small business in different sectors and the importance of the cross-section of regions are among the priorities of the researches being carried out in this regard.

In the new Uzbekistan, attention is paid to the wide use of the improvement of the structural structure of small businesses in the modernization of leading industries and ensuring the competitiveness of the national economy. In particular, in accordance with the government decision adopted on September 14, 2023, the state budget and international financial institutions will allocate 6 trillion soums and 1.2 billion US dollars for the development of small businesses in 2023-2026, and these funds will be used for continuous support programs for small business entities. is being routed through. The state has simplified the mechanisms of providing microloans for small business entities, microloans are allocated for a period of 7 years with preferential 3-year payments and placed at a rate two percentage points lower than the main rate of the Central Bank [1]. In the effective implementation of these tasks, further improvement of the economic content of the concept of "structural structure of small business", improvement of the method of evaluating the level of efficiency of the structural structure of small business according to the types of economic activity, based on theoretical rules, development of the method of determining the efficiency of the structural structure of small business according to the types of economic activity, improving the method of assessing the efficiency of the formation of the structural structure of small businesses, Based on the improvement of the structural structure of small entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan, it shows the relevance of scientific research aimed at developing a long-term forecast of the main activity indicators of the sector.

2.Literature review.

Various aspects of small business activity are discussed by many scientists of foreign countries, including Anikina V.V., Gryaznova A.G., Borodina E.A. Krasnov D.A., Lapusta M.G., Salina O.V., Starostin Yu.L., Khait M.M. and others [2,3,4,5,6,7]. Peculiarities of participation of small business in foreign economic activities, including foreign trade activities Alyokhina O.V., Ermilov I.S., Poroshin Yu.B., Ivanov S.V., Petrov A.A., Kuznetsova E.V. , Morkovina S.S., Kuzmenko N.I., Mikhalkova I.G., Kuchukov R.R., Nureev R.M., Samigullin E.V., Siverskaya Ya.V., Shalygina N.P., Teplov A.A., Fomina I.V., Sharapov K.V., Shved A.V., Shut P.A., shcherbakova N.A. and researched in the scientific works of a number of other foreign economists and specialists [8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20].

Development of small business sector and its participation in foreign economic activity Bakieva I.A., Zakirov F.Sh., Ibragimov F.A., Ibragimova M.M., Rasulmukhammedov A.D., Sultanova G.K., Yuldashev D. T., Gafurov U.V. and others [21,22,23,24].

Recognizing the importance of the scientific ideas and conclusions put forward in the researches of the above-mentioned scientists and specialists, the existence of aspects that require the research of the scientific and methodological bases of increasing the effectiveness of the participation of small business entities in foreign trade activities in the current conditions determines the relevance of this dissertation work.

3.Methodology

Scientific research methods such as scientific abstraction, analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction, statistical grouping, monographic research, and comparison were used in the development of basic scientific and theoretical rules.

4. Analysis and results

Based on different approaches to the formation of the structural structure of the small business sector in the economy expressed in the scientific literature, the following main aspects can be stated:

1) small entrepreneurship is a specific sector of the economy, which is formed within the boundaries of enterprises in various industries and sectors according to certain defined criteria;

2) the boundaries of the small business category, that is, the scope of the small business sector may vary under the influence of subjective factors;

3) the structural structure of the economy is formed according to a number of main aspects (for example, sector (field), ownership, organizational-legal and management form, size of the enterprise, etc.), and this situation also affects the structural structure of the small business sector within it. ;

4) although the structural structure of the small business sector is relatively abstract, prone to subjective influence, it also has objective foundations;

5) the level of acceptability of the structural structure of the small business sector has a significant impact on the economic efficiency of the enterprises in the field.

It can be seen that the formation of the structural structure of the small business sector in the economy is important for regulation. In organizing this process, it is possible to single out the main factors influencing the formation of the structural structure of small business (Fig. 1).

Fig.1. The main factors affecting the formation of the structural structure of small business [25]

Despite the fact that the small business sector is an integral and integral part of the national economy, due to the specific characteristics of the sector, some economic events and processes also show laws that are expressed in a private way. Although the structural structure of small business can be divided into functional, branch, regional (territorial), socio-economic, external economic structures, like the structural structure of the national economy, there are certain differences in terms of their specific manifestation. Based on this, the following author's definition of the economic content of the concept of "small business structural structure" can be given: "Small business structural structure is a specific economic activity that operates in the context of general economic conditions and limitations of natural and legal description in terms of its main activity. a set of structures of economic subjects specialized and formed in a certain proportion according to their functional, network, regional (territorial), socio-economic, foreign economic and other characteristics" .

Wider use of small business and private entrepreneurship is important for ensuring stable economic development in Uzbekistan. For this, it is appropriate to regulate the specialization of small business enterprises by sector.

In order to ensure that these processes are carried out smoothly and consistently,

and structural imbalances do not occur in the country's economy as a result of the effect of structural changes, the state should effectively establish a network policy.

Network policy is a sub-system of the state socio-economic policy aimed at the joint management of the development of economic sectors with private business, the distribution of financial resources between sectors, and the use of administrative, regulatory and financial levers of regulation.

The objectives of the network policy can be determined based on the following criteria and directions: 1) a particular network or type of activity; 2) the position of the branch in the world, domestic and regional markets: a) volume of production, share; b) product quality and competitiveness; 3) wear and tear of equipment; 4) assortment of products and services; 5) efficiency of branch enterprises; 6) network life cycle stage.

Thus, the following can be considered the goals of the structural policy: 1) stabilization and strengthening of the state of industries; 2) ensuring the growth of the network; 3) modernization; 4) increase the competitiveness of network products and services; 5) reorganization and restructuring of branch enterprises; 6) increase the efficiency of branch enterprises; 7) slowing down the rate of growth of the industry (in the case of production surplus, "overheating" of the economy); 8) limiting production activity (at the end of the network life cycle, when it loses the competition).

Functionally, sectoral policy affects areas of the economic system that are not covered by monetary-credit, tax-budget, currency, antimonopoly, infrastructure, conjuncture, investment, social, environmental and other subsystems of management. In the implementation of the network policy, improvement of these directions takes place through the structure of the economy.

The following are the objects of network policy: 1) types of economic activity; 2) networks; territorial-network complexes, inter-network complexes; 4) enterprises.

The following are the subjects of the network policy: 1) the state; 2) network business; 3) scientific institutes.

The industry policy of the state should be aimed at stimulating the development of industries that make up the regional economy, and its priority task is to significantly accelerate the structural changes in the market-based specialized industries of the region.

Currently, not all departments and ministries of network or industry management in our country have their own clearly developed network policies. It is true that the strategies of the leading sectors for a certain period were developed in cases of state demand, but this process was carried out more in the description of the statement of the general goal.

The analysis of the economic activities of the leading industries and sectors in our country shows that in the development of the industry policy, the activities of its economic entities as a coherent and coordinated integrated system were left out of consideration. For example, the adopted measures are often aimed at large and state-owned economic entities. The small business sector is rarely covered by these regulations.

Accordingly, in our opinion, the official management office or ministry of each sector should use the opportunities of small business in effectively organizing the activities of the sector under its management. First of all, it is necessary to ensure a healthy competitive environment in the network, for this purpose, to organize sufficient level of small business entities, if the competition becomes unreasonably intense, then it is necessary to take measures to limit excessive "pressure" on the network.

Regulation of the processes of specialization of small business enterprises by sector provides for the following measures:

- to ensure the freedom of choosing the type of small business activity;
- ensuring the freedom of inter-sectoral movement of business capital;
- ensuring transparency and openness of economic, commercial and financial information on the network;

- creating an opportunity for the formation of a healthy competitive environment and equality of economic conditions in each industry;

- improper functioning of market mechanisms, inappropriate spending of economic resources due to subjective reasons, prevention and elimination of economic stagnation and stagnation, etc.

In researching ways to improve the structural structure of small business in Uzbekistan, it is important to ensure the smoothness of the formation of the structural structure of small business. Stability of economic processes means stable and continuous development of economic activity, maintaining balance despite changes and various economic conditions. Stability ensures the internal stability of the economic system, long-term growth and socio-economic development.

It is important to pay attention to the following main factors in ensuring the smooth formation of the structural structure of small businesses in the sectors of the economy of Uzbekistan:

- 1) stability of the legal framework and other legal documents regulating small business activities;
- 2) stability of financial markets and reliability of the banking system;
- 3) efficiency of small business production capacity;
- 4) harmonization of state economic policies (including tax policy, customs policy and other regulatory mechanisms) in relation to small business;
- 5) competitive environment and freedom of market specialization processes;
- 6) development of small business infrastructure.

If changes in the structural structure of small businesses are consistent with the indicators and results of their economic activity, this situation can be considered consistent with the principle of consistency. This situation can be determined by the following formula:

$$M_{TT} = \sum_{i=1}^n SS_{i1} \times K_{i1} - \sum_{i=1}^n SS_{i0} \times K_{i0};$$

here:

M_{TT} - the regularity of the formation of the structural structure of small business;

SS_{i0} is the comparative weight of branch i in the structural structure of small business in the base period;

SS_{i1} - the comparative weight of branch i in the structural structure of small business during the reporting period;

K_{i0} - indicator of economic activity of the i branch as a result of the change in the structural structure of small business in the base period;

K_{i1} - indicator of economic activity of industry i as a result of changes in the structural structure of small businesses during the reporting period;

i - sectors in the structural structure of small business.

Based on this formula, the following results can be obtained:

$M_{TT} > 0$ – changes in the structure of small business in accordance with the principle of regularity;

$M_{TT} = 0$ – there are no changes in the structural structure of small business or their effect is not significant;

$M_{TT} < 0$ – changes in the structure of small business are not in accordance with the principle of regularity.

Ensuring the regularity of the formation of the structural structure of small business depends on the continuity, efficiency and reliability of the economic policy in the field, and is the basis of long-term economic growth.

It is important to approach in terms of separate, special blocks when determining measures to improve the efficiency of the structural structure of small businesses in Uzbekistan. In our opinion, the overall picture of the blocks and their content in this regard can be expressed as follows (Fig. 2).

Block 1: Financial support

- preferential loans;
- attraction of investments;
- tax benefits

Block 2: Improvement of production

- introduction of innovations and technologies;
- product diversification;
- cooperation of small enterprises

Block 3: Training of personnel

- educational and educational programs in the field of entrepreneurship;
- training of qualified personnel;
- sharing experience

Fig.2. Approach in terms of special blocks in determining measures to improve the efficiency of the structural structure of small business [25].

These measures help to improve the efficiency of the structural structure of small business and strengthen its competitiveness.

Based on Figure 2, it is important to evaluate the effectiveness of the small business structure in terms of special blocks. In this case, in our opinion, it is appropriate to evaluate the effectiveness of each specific block and of individual measures within the block as a ratio of the result of changes in this regard (N) to the costs (SX) in this direction (Table 1).

Table-1

Кичик тадбиркорлик таркибий тузилмаси самарадорлигини блоклар ҳамда муайян блок доирасидаги чора-тадбир бўйича баҳолаш [25].

Blocks	For Block	On a case-by-case basis
Block 1: Financial support (MQQ)	$S_{MQQ} = \frac{N_{MQQ}}{SX_{MQQ}}$	$S_{IK} = \frac{N_{IK}}{IK_{TT}}; S_I = \frac{N_I}{I_{TT}}; S_{SI} = \frac{N_{SI}}{SI_{TT}};$ <p>IK - preferential loans; I - investment attraction; SI - tax credits.</p>
Block 2: Production Improvement (ICHT)	$S_{ICHT} = \frac{N_{ICHT}}{SX_{ICHT}}$	$S_{IT} = \frac{N_{IT}}{IT_{TT}}; S_{MD} = \frac{N_{MD}}{MD_{TT}}; S_H = \frac{N_H}{H_{TT}};$ <p>IT - introduction of innovations and technologies; MD - product diversification; H - cooperation of small enterprises.</p>
Block 3: Personnel training (KMO)	$S_{KMO} = \frac{N_{KMO}}{SX_{KMO}}$	$S_{TD} = \frac{N_{TD}}{TD_{TT}}; S_{MKT} = \frac{N_{MKT}}{MKT_{TT}}; S_{TA} = \frac{N_{TA}}{TA_{TT}};$ <p>TD - education and training programs in the field of entrepreneurship; MKT - training of qualified personnel; TA - sharing experience.</p>
Block 4: Reducing administrative barriers (MTK)	$S_{MTK} = \frac{N_{MTK}}{SX_{MTK}}$	$S_{BO} = \frac{N_{BO}}{BO_{TT}}; S_{MK} = \frac{N_{MK}}{MK_{TT}}; S_{DXSH} = \frac{N_{DXSH}}{DXSH_{TT}};$ <p>BO - simplification of opening a business; MK - improvement of the administrative support system;</p>

		PPP - public-private partnership mechanisms.
Block 5: Market Infrastructure Development (BIR)	$S_{BIR} = \frac{N_{BIR}}{SX_{BIR}}$	$S_{AMT} = \frac{N_{AMT}}{AMT_{TT}}; S_{MSZ} = \frac{N_{MSZ}}{MSZ_{TT}};$ AMT - communication and information systems for entrepreneurs; MSZ - special industrial zones for small enterprises.
Block 6: Marketing and Export Capacity Building (MES)	$S_{MES} = \frac{N_{MES}}{SX_{MES}}$	$S_{MST} = \frac{N_{MST}}{MST_{TT}}; S_E = \frac{N_E}{E_{TT}};$ MST - improvement of marketing strategy; E - export orientation.

Market and administrative support are important in regulating the formation of small business structure. These two approaches regulate entrepreneurship through the following methods (Figure 3).

It can be seen from Figure 3 that usually small business entities operate in relatively free market conditions and try to strengthen their place and position in the market through competition. Accordingly, it is important to influence the formation of the structural structure of small businesses in Uzbekistan by improving the competitive environment.

Fig.3. The main levers of regulating the formation of the structural structure of small business [25].

Although the tax policy implemented through tax rates and benefits shows an administrative lever in form, it is a market lever in content. It has a significant impact on the formation of the structural structure of small businesses by creating tax breaks to attract investments to the sector and support entrepreneurship.

Access to new markets for small entrepreneurs or development within existing markets is largely determined by market entry opportunities. In this case, market-related forms of these opportunities are used - such channels as trade fairs, exhibitions, online market platforms.

It is possible to influence the formation of an optimal structural structure of small business by providing various funds, credit, financial and consulting support within the framework of state support programs. Also, this goal can be more clearly achieved by establishing laws and regulations of an administrative description by the state, developing special requirements for business formalization and licensing. The clearer and more transparent the laws and regulations are, the more favorable the business environment will be.

The provision of technical assistance by the state and the creation of a set of

relevant infrastructure (for example, special zones, production infrastructure and technical assistance centers, etc.) can play a specific guiding role in forming an effective structural structure of small business.

5.Conclusions

Although the structural structure of small business can be divided into functional, branch, regional (territorial), socio-economic, external economic structures, like the structural structure of the national economy, there are certain differences in terms of their specific manifestation. Based on this, the following author's definition of the economic content of the concept of "small business structural structure" can be given: "Small business structural structure is a specific economic activity that operates in the context of general economic conditions and limitations of natural and legal description in terms of its main activity. a set of structures of economic subjects specialized and formed in a certain proportion according to their functional, network, regional (territorial), socio-economic, foreign economic and other characteristics" .

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It is possible to influence the formation of an optimal structural structure of small business by providing various funds, credit, financial and consulting support within the framework of state support programs. Also, this goal can be more clearly achieved by establishing laws and regulations of an administrative description by the state, developing special requirements for business formalization and licensing.

References:

1. Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-312 of 09.07.2024. On measures to improve the complex program "Continuous support of small business". - <https://lex.uz/docs/7093832>
2. Anikin V.V. Small business in the context of globalization: problems and development prospects. - M.: Economica, 2020.;
3. Gryaznova A.G., Borodina, E.A. Economic mechanisms for supporting small business in Russia. - St. Petersburg: Piter, 2019.;
4. Krasnov D.A. State support for small business in Russia and abroad. - M.: Yurait, 2018.; Lapusta M.G. Entrepreneurship. - Textbook for universities. - M.: INFRA-M, 2017.;
5. Salina O.V. Development of small business in the digital economy. - M.: Alpina Publisher, 2021.;
6. Starostin Yu.L. Small business. - Textbook. - M.: INFRA-M, 1997.;
7. Khait M.M. Development of small business based on the restructuring of large enterprises // Vestn. Mosk. University. - Series. 6; Economy. - 2006. - No. 4. - P. 32-43.
8. Alekhova O.V., Ermilov I.S., Poroshin Yu.B. Development of small enterprises in the field of international business. // Economics and management of the national economy. - P. 35.;
9. Ivanov S.V., Petrov A.A. Factors of successful entry of small enterprises into international markets. // Bulletin of international trade, 2021, No. 2, pp. 45-56.;
10. Kuznetsova E.V., Morkovina S.S. Export-oriented small entrepreneurship: problems and directions for their solution. - <https://scienceforum.ru>;
11. Kuzmenko N.I., Mikhalkova I.G. The role of small business in Russia in foreign trade activities. // Ekonominfo. 2018. Vol. 15. No. 1. – P. 81.;

- 12.Kuchukov RR Small and medium business: problems, trends, prospects and strategies of the exit to the international market // Small and medium business: problems, tendencies, prospects and strategies of the exit to the international market. - <https://core.ac.uk>;
- 13.Nureyev RM Foreign economic activity: theory and practice. - Moscow: Dashkov i K, 2020 .; Samigullin EV Foreign trade efficiency coefficient // Bulletin of science and creativity. 2016. No. 4 (4). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru>;
- 14.Siverskaya Ya.V., Shalygina NP Foreign trade activity as an integral part of Russia's foreign economic activity. - <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/151228053.pdf>;
- 15.Teplov A.A. Innovative strategies for the development of small enterprises in international markets. // Journal of Innovative Economics, 2020, No. 4, pp. 102-114.;
- 16.Fomina I.V. Small entrepreneurship: strategy and tactics of foreign economic activity. - St. Petersburg: SpetsLit, 2019.;
- 17.Sharapov K.V. Methods for increasing the competitiveness of small enterprises in international trade. // Economic analysis: theory and practice, 2018, No. 6, pp. 89-98.;
- 18.Shved A.V. Foreign trade efficiency: approaches to statistical assessment. Questions of statistics. 2020;27(4):88-96.;
- 19.Shut' P.A. Features and problems of export activities of small and medium-sized businesses in Russia. // Siberian trade and economic journal, No. 2 (20), 2015. - P. 112.;
- 20.Shcherbakova N.A. Small business and foreign economic activity: challenges and solutions. - M .: Finance and statistics, 2021.
21. Bakieva I.A. Development of small business and private entrepreneurship in the light industry of Uzbekistan. Dis. ... iqt. science. name - T., 2012.;

22. Ibragimova M.M. Improving the efficiency of small business and private entrepreneurship based on structural changes (in the case of Namangan region).

Autoref. ... iqt. Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) - T., 2018.;

23. Yuldashev D.T. Improving the economic mechanism of family business development. Autoref. ... iqt. Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) - T., 2019;

24. Gafurov U.V. Improvement of economic mechanisms of state regulation of small business. Monograph. - Tashkent: Finance, 2016. - 208 p.